

**OPTIMIZATION OF TREATMENT OF PATIENTS WITH INCREASED
TOOTH ERASURE BASED ON THE FUNCTIONAL STATE OF THE
DENTAL SYSTEM AND POSTURAL STATUS**

Zikirova Hulkar Alisherovna

Burxonova Zараfruz Qobilovna

Samarkand State Medical University

Annotation:The clinical picture of increased tooth abrasion is covered in detail in the literature, however, there are only isolated data on the relationship between functional disorders of the dental system and the musculoskeletal system.

Restoring the functions of the chewing apparatus with increased tooth abrasion is an important task, which requires constant improvement of diagnostic and therapeutic measures. (Lebedenko, 2006; Gu Y. et al., 2000; Keles A., 2002).

Thus, a new approach is required to study the nature of functional disorders occurring in patients with increased tooth abrasion. In this aspect, it seems to us relevant to assess the functional features of the dental system and the entire musculoskeletal system in order to develop new methods of diagnosis and treatment of this pathology.

Keywords: tooth erasure, postural status, tooth abrasion

The purpose of the study:Improvement of orthopedic treatment of patients with increased tooth abrasion based on consideration of the functional state of the dental system and postural status.

Research materials and methods:As part of our study, we examined the results of the examination and treatment of 50 patients with increased tooth abrasion who sought dental care. All the subjects were divided into two groups. The comparison group consisted of 20 patients without signs of increased tooth abrasion and pronounced functional disorders of the ESR.

The main group included 50 patients with increased tooth abrasion aged 35 to 54 years, which corresponds to the average age according to the WHO classification. Depending on the therapy performed, the main group was divided into two subgroups:

1. The first subgroup included 30 patients with increased tooth erasure who were treated based on the results of functional analysis of the dental and postural systems.

2. The second subgroup included 20 people with increased tooth erasure who were treated according to the traditional scheme.

The results of the study:As a result of the clinical examination, it was revealed that patients with increased tooth erasure complained of aesthetic defects (34 patients out of 50), discomfort when chewing (27 patients out of 50), tension in the chewing muscles (17 patients out of 50), unstable position of the lower jaw (23 patients out of 50), asymmetric mouth opening (24 patients out of 50) , dental hypersensitivity (20 patients out of 50), noise phenomena in the temporomandibular joint (10 patients out of 50).

On external examination, 19 people had pronounced nasolabial and chin folds, 16 of whom had a decrease in bite height by 4 mm. When examining the oral cavity, it should be noted that 41 people had tooth prints on the side surfaces of the tongue or on the mucous membrane of the cheeks.

Chronic generalized periodontitis of mild severity was observed in 15 people. Wedge-shaped defects were observed in 29 people of the main group. Carious lesions of hard tissues were found in 45 people of the main group. Therapeutic and orthopedic restorations that did not meet clinical requirements were determined in 36 patients. In all patients of the main group, facets of erasure were determined on the lateral and frontal sections of the dentition.

Comparative palpation of the masticatory muscles revealed soreness of the anterior bundles of the temporal muscle in 40% of the subjects. Severe pain was

found in 13%. A comparative analysis of palpation of the superficial part of the masticatory muscle showed that moderate palpation soreness was found in 35%. In 65% of mild severity. In 63% of patients, moderate and mild soreness was determined by palpation of the lateral and medial pterygoid muscles. It should be noted that patients with increased erasure quite often had soreness during palpation of the scapulohyoid and sternocleidomastoid muscles. In 67% of the patients noted tension in these muscle groups. Palpation of the atlanto-occipital junction was painful in 43%. Thus, it can be concluded that in patients with increased tooth erasure, in addition to tension and pain in the masticatory muscles, uncomfortable sensations in the neck muscles are noted, this indicates an inextricable relationship between the maxillary system and the musculoskeletal system. This fact is also confirmed by the data of domestic and foreign researchers. Conducting an analysis of electromyography in patients with increased erasure (n=50), we evaluated the indices of symmetry of the chewing muscles and temporal muscles (ISChM), lateral displacement index (ILD), static stabilizing occlusal index (ISSO). Index values in patients of the comparison group (n=20) ranged from 80 to 120%. In patients of the main group, which included 50 people with increased tooth erasure, we determined the deviation of varying degrees of severity from the comparison group of the values of heart failure in 20 people. In 30 subjects (60%), index values are determined in the boundary intervals of the norm. The ISM was changed in 34 patients of the main group. In 16 patients (32%), the index values were in the normal range. Deviations in the index were observed in 18 of the surveyed main group. In 32 patients (64%), the index values were in the normal range. As for the ISSO, in 33 patients of the main group, the values differed from those of the comparison group. In 17 patients (34%), the index values were in the normal range. It should be noted that in patients with normal values of heart rate and deviations in heart rate and heart rate were observed, as a rule, of mild to moderate severity. Based on the analysis of the primary data, it can be concluded that there are functional changes in the masticatory muscles, which manifests itself in a

change in their activity. When analyzing the data of computer stabilometry in patients with increased erasure, we estimated the following parameters: the area of the statokinesiogram (S), the average speed of movement of the central nervous system (V), the average position of the central nervous system, deviation of the central nervous system.

Table 1. Comparative characteristics of the stabilometric parameters in the studied groups

	The group is dichotomous		Arithmetical mean	Standard deviation	The standard error of the average	
The standard deviation of the ASD in the frontal plane	research group	0	21,9964	21,15255	2,99142	,003
	The control group	0	11,1290	8,41681	1,88206	
The standard deviation of the ASD in the sagittal plane	research group	0	52,2432	75,52727	10,68117	,046
	The control group	0	28,7045	19,96371	4,46402	
The speed of the ASD	research group	0	19,4450	10,52359	1,48826	0,001
	The control group	0	12,6285	2,03597	,45526	
The area of the	research group	0	242,1792	293,48811	41,50549	,00

statokinesiogram is 90	The control group	0	107,2 885	37,6 0498	8,40873	2
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Based on the analysis of the data of the electromyographic study in dynamics, it can be concluded that there was a significant improvement in all the main parameters in patients of the first subgroup (n=30) after treatment. Most of the electromyographic indices were in the normal range, or there were minor functional abnormalities of mild severity. It should be noted that there is a small percentage of patients with severe abnormalities. In the second subgroup, positive dynamics is also noted, but not as pronounced as in patients of the first subgroup, since there remains a fairly large percentage of patients with deviations of moderate and severe severity of functional disorders of the masticatory muscles. The approximation of the indices to the normal intervals indicates the stabilization of the functional state after the restoration of the functional surfaces of the teeth in patients with increased tooth abrasion. Thus, these studies confirm the fact that the activity of the chewing muscles is controlled by the proprioceptor apparatus of the teeth. With the loss of hard tissues due to increased erasure, there is a change in normal activity and a violation of the coordinated work of the masticatory muscles.

Conclusions. Based on the conducted clinical examination, it was revealed that patients with increased tooth erasure most often complained of aesthetic defects (68%), discomfort when chewing (54%), tension in the masticatory muscles (34%), unstable position of the lower jaw (46%), asymmetric mouth opening (48%), hypersensitivity teeth (40%), noise phenomena in the temporomandibular joint (20%). When examining the oral cavity, wedge-shaped defects were observed in 58% of the subjects of the main group. Carious lesions of hard tissues were found in 90% of the main group of people. Therapeutic and orthopedic restorations that did not meet clinical requirements were determined in 72% of patients. In all patients of the main group, facets of erasure were determined on the lateral and frontal sections of the dentition.

Literature:

1. Ризаев Ж. А., Ахмедов А. А. ОСНОВЫ СТОМАТОЛОГИЧЕСКОЙ ПОМОЩИ В РЕСПУБЛИКЕ УЗБЕКИСТАН НА ОСНОВЕ РАЗВИТИЯ ОБЩЕЙ ВРАЧЕБНОЙ ПРАКТИКИ //ЖУРНАЛ СТОМАТОЛОГИИ И КРАНИОФАЦИАЛЬНЫХ ИССЛЕДОВАНИЙ. – 2023. – Т. 4. – №. 3.
2. Ризаев Ж. А., Ахмедов А. А. GROWTH AND DEVELOPMENT OF GENERAL MEDICAL PRACTICE IN THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN TO IMPROVE DENTAL CARE //ЖУРНАЛ СТОМАТОЛОГИИ И КРАНИОФАЦИАЛЬНЫХ ИССЛЕДОВАНИЙ. – 2023. – Т. 4. – №. 3.
3. Astanovich A. D. A. et al. The State of Periodontal Tissues in Athletes Engaged in Cyclic Sports //Annals of the Romanian Society for Cell Biology. – 2021. – С. 235-241.
4. Alimjanovich R. J., Astanovich A. A. СОВЕРШЕНТСТВО ВАНИЕ СТОМАТОЛОГИЧЕСКОЙ ПОМОЩИ В УЗБЕКИСТАНЕ С ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЕМ КОНЦЕПТУАЛЬНОГО ПОДХОДА ДЛЯ УЛУЧШЕНИЕ ЕЕ КАЧЕСТВА //JOURNAL OF BIOMEDICINE AND PRACTICE. – 2023. – Т. 8. – №. 4.
5. Ортикова Н. Глобализация биоэтики в период пандемии COVID-19 //Общество и инновации. – 2020. – Т. 1. – №. 1/S. – С. 677-682.
6. Ортикова Н. Влияние психоэмоционального напряжения детей на состояние здоровья полости рта //Общество и инновации. – 2023. – Т. 4. – №. 7/S. – С. 328-333.
7. Ортикова Н. Х., Ризаев Ж. А., Мелибаев Б. А. ПСИХОЛОГИЧЕСКИЕ АСПЕКТЫ ПОСТРОЕНИЯ СТОМАТОЛОГИЧЕСКОГО ПРИЕМА ПАЦИЕНТОВ ДЕТСКОГО ВОЗРАСТА //EDITOR COORDINATOR. – 2021. – С. 554.
8. Ортикова Н. Тенденция эффективности профилактических мероприятий путем коррекции психологического стресса у детей на

стоматологическом приёме //Общество и инновации. – 2022. – Т. 3. – №. 6. – С. 181-189.

9. Fakhridin C., Shokhrub S., Nilufar I. ENDOKANAL PIN-KONSTRUKSIYALARNI ISHLATISHDA ASORATLAR VA XATOLAR TAHLILI //JOURNAL OF BIOMEDICINE AND PRACTICE. – 2022. – Т. 7. – №. 1.

10. Shoxrux S., Shoxrux I., Faxriddin C. PREVENTION AND TREATMENT OF ORAL INFECTIONS IN DENTURE WEARERS //International Journal of Early Childhood Special Education. – 2022. – Т. 14. – №. 4.

11. Xusanovich C. F. COMPLETE REMOVABLE PROSTHESIS SUPPORTED BY IMPLANTS //European International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research and Management Studies. – 2023. – Т. 3. – №. 11. – С. 127-133.

12. Xusanovich C. F. et al. PROSTHETICS A COMPLETE REMOVABLE PROSTHESIS BASED ON IMPLANTS //European International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research and Management Studies. – 2023. – Т. 3. – №. 11. – С. 122-126.

13. Sevinch E., Zarafruz B. ETIOLOGICAL TREATMENT FEATURES INFLAMMATORY PERIODONTAL DISEASE //European International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research and Management Studies. – 2024. – Т. 4. – №. 03. – С. 241-246.

14. Yusufboy S., Qobilovna B. Z. FEATURES OF THE STRUCTURE OF COPD IN ELDERLY PATIENTS //European International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research and Management Studies. – 2024. – Т. 4. – №. 05. – С. 363-368.

15. Yusufboy S., Qobilovna B. Z. STUDY THE EFFECT OF HYGIENIC CARE ON THE MICROBIAL LANDSCAPE OF THE ORAL CAVITY IN PATIENTS USING COMBINED SPLINTING STRUCTURES WITH

MODERATE PERIODONTITIS //European International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research and Management Studies. – 2024. – T. 4. – №. 02. – C. 50-55.

16. Sevinch E., Qobilovna B. Z. A STUDY ON THE MORPHOFUNCTIONAL STATE OF ORAL ORGAN TISSUES DURING THE USE OF NON-REMOVABLE ORTHODONTIC STRUCTURES //European International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research and Management Studies. – 2024. – T. 4. – №. 03. – C. 247-253.

17. Shaximardonova E. S., Kobilovna B. Z. RED LICHEN PLANUS OF THE ORAL MUCOSA AND ITS CLINICAL ANALYSIS OF A PATIENT WITH, ASSOCIATED WITH THE EPSTEIN—BARR VIRUS //European International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research and Management Studies. – 2024. – T. 4. – №. 01. – C. 272-279.

18. Yusufboy S., Qobilovna B. Z. STUDY OF CHANGES IN THE ORAL CAVITY IN ENDOCRINE DISEASES //European International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research and Management Studies. – 2024. – T. 4. – №. 05. – C. 357-362.

19. Yusufboy S., Qobilovna B. Z. SMARTBURS II—A REVIEW OF THE ADVANTAGES OF SMART BOR //European International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research and Management Studies. – 2024. – T. 4. – №. 02. – C. 56-60.